

INDIVIDUALIZATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE MIDDLE LEVEL.

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Annotation

Modern training, including foreign languages, is investigated in this article, focused on a medium-sized student. Based on many studies and personal observations, it can be said that schooling does not pay due attention to the individual characteristics of students, which is why weak students become unsuitable, and strong lose interest in the subject. That is why the issue of individualized learning becomes relevant, especially in teaching foreign languages due to group form of training.

Keywords: Individualization of learning, differentiation, method, contradiction, education, educational standards, skills, personalization, socially deterministic category, pedagogical category, methodical category.

Individualization of training remains an urgent topic for many scientists and teachers despite the fact that it has been studied enough. Many scientists, such as A. Kirsanov, I. E. Unt, N. M. Shamakhaev, E. I. Passov, determined the phenomenology of individualization in his writings, distinguished its differences with differentiation, developed technologies and techniques for the use of individualization in learning various disciplines. Despite the sufficient development of the problem, issues remain that require continuing research. It is especially acute the issue of using various teaching techniques, corresponding to an individualized approach in foreign language training due to the special place of discipline "Foreign Language" among the school course items. Obstacles to the use of individualization in training in foreign language are caused by a number of contradictions:

1. contradiction between the individual process of assimilation of the foreign language and the group form of the organization's organization;
2. contradiction between methods and techniques of work in the group and numerous individual characteristics inherent in a specific learning;
3. contradiction between the actual load of the teacher and the great complexity in the implementation of individualization of training.

These contradictions lead to the need to further explore opportunities to individualize the training of a foreign language. Thus, the object of our study is the process of teaching English in the middle level, the subject of research is the ways of individualization in the learning

process of English.

The purpose of the qualification work is to systematize the methods and techniques of individualization in teaching English in the middle level.

The purpose of the study, the object and the subject caused the formation of the following hypothesis: the comprehensive implementation of the principle of individualization in the English language learning process contributes to the more efficient development of the foreign language communicative competence of students, and also creates conditions for self-realization. On the way to achieving the goal, it is advisable to solve the following tasks:

1. explore the purpose and content of the training of foreign language at the average level;
2. consider the concept of individualization in teaching English and compare it with such concepts as differentiation and personalization;
3. investigate ways of individualization in English lessons;
4. conduct analysis for the average level for the use of individualization methods and techniques;
5. organize and conduct trial training at school;
6. develop recommendations on the use of individualization methods and techniques in English lessons.

Objectives and content of learning English

A modern education system is a single targeted process of upbringing and learning, as well as a set of acquired knowledge, skills, skills, value installations, functions, experience and competencies aimed at finding and implementing variability, individualization. If we turn to the pedagogical dictionary, we will find the following definition: "Education is an integral part and at the same time a product of socialization". This means that education is constantly in dynamic development and should always comply with the goals and objectives that form society. At the moment, the development of society is very important to integrate all aspects of life, the convergence of knowledge and therefore the development of such skills as "Hard Skills" and "Soft Skills" is set to a strong position. Where "Hard Skills" - professional skills that can be learned and which can be measured. "Soft Skills" is universal competencies that are much more difficult to measure quantitative indicators.

To date, there is no single interpretation of the concepts of flexible and professional skills. In its study, we will rely on the Oxford dictionary, which says that "flexible skills are personal qualities of a person who make it possible to interact with other people more efficiently and harmoniously". "Professional skills are the skills that are relatively easy to measure and are often confirmed by a certain qualifications".

If we talk about "Hard Skills" (hard or professional skills), then many scientists agree that they can be measured in contrast to "flexible skills". So, D. Tatarshikova believes that "Hard Skills is the skills associated with the vehicle technique that can be visually demonstrated". A. I. Kanardov determines professional skills as "Technical skills related to the work performed in the field of formalized technologies: office work, logistics, blind printing method, car management, programming, and the like".

Stripping from the above definitions, it can be concluded that "Hard Skills" is the ability to perform certain tasks; Technical skills that can be demonstrated clearly. "Hard Skills" is all skills directly related to the activity that a person is currently involved. Moreover, many scientists agree that in contrast to flexible skills, they can be measured.

Apparently, in order to develop professional and flexible skills, the ability to develop and

apply individual educational routes in practice, which will further contribute to the development of students and their personal growth.

"An individual educational route is a targeted projected, differentiated, educational program that provides a learning position of the subject of choice, developing and implementing the educational program in the implementation of teachers of pedagogical support for its self-determination and self-realization".

Individualization becomes a leading methodological approach to achieve the planned results by each studying in the implementation of state educational standards (SES). Due to insufficient examination of individualization and a variety of approaches to it, this phenomenon is actively discussed by methodologists and teachers.

State educational standards of basic general education in the form of state requirements are built, a certain level of mastering the material studied, and also create a system of universal training actions and conditions that guarantee their achievement. The main task of educational institutions is to determine the strategy for the implementation of individualization within the framework of the SES, in the content of which "read" the importance of the development of "flexible" skills and professional skills.

The main goal of the SES is to create such conditions under which the strategic task of public education will be solved. In other words, a significant improvement in the quality of education, an increase and acquiring qualitatively new educational results corresponding to the request of the personality, society and the state.

State Educational Standard places three groups of requirements:

1. Requirements for the structure of the main educational program of basic general education.

A) Development of its own educational program, curriculum, as well as accounting for requests and wishes of parents and schoolchildren by each educational institution.

2. Requirements for the results of the development of the main educational program of basic general education.

A) Personal: The readiness of students to self-development, the development of internal motivation for learning and knowledge.

B) Metasubjects: Mastering educational universal learning actions that help develop key competencies.

B) Subjects: Mastering the learning experience characteristic of a particular subject, the transformation of this experience and the ability to apply it in practice.

3. Requirements for the conditions for the implementation of the main educational program of basic general education:

A) Ensuring the achievements of the objectives of the main general education, its high quality, availability and openness for students, their parents (legal representatives) and the whole society, spiritual and moral development and education.

B) Guaranteeing and strengthening the physical, psychological and social health of students;

B) The continuity in relation to primary general education and taking into account the characteristics of the organization of basic general education, as well as the specifics of the age psychophysical development of students in obtaining basic general education.

Since the SES focuses on individualization, each educational institution creates its own educational program, focusing on the following stages of the implementation proposed by the Ministry of Education:

1. The study of the individual abilities of each trainee.

2. The study of educational needs on the part of students and their parents.
3. Creating groups of students in similar individual characteristics.
4. Detection of students with high creative and intellectual abilities and learning disabilities.
5. Selection of a possible strategy for implementing individualization in the English language lesson.
6. Analysis and assessment of the effectiveness of the implementation of individualization in the chosen educational institution.

Thus, having studied and analyzing the standards of training, we consider it important to note that the organization of individualization is part of learning.

To date, the purpose of learning is defined as "a pre-planned result of pedagogical activity achieved with the help of various techniques, methods and means of training". The purpose of learning is the central kernel, from which any teacher will begin to repel. It is from the awareness and determination of the goal begins the development of a methodological plan. Knowing what factors affect the target, we can more fully define the goal as a phenomenon. It seems to us as:

- 1) A socially deterministic category, which is determined in the context of the value system adopted in society and taking into account the needs of society and its individual citizens in the study of foreign languages.
- 2) Pedagogical category, since its consideration should be carried out in the context of the general education concept adopted in society at a certain stage of its development and development of the school system as a whole.
- 3) The methodical category, in the formulation of which the main provisions of the technique and scientific provisions of other sciences associated with the methodological science are taken into account.

From the point of view of the methodological category, the strategic goal in the field of training in foreign languages is currently defined as the creation of conditions for the formation and development of the individual with the help of the language under study.

Also, according to N. D. Galskova, at present, the technique goes to the field of education in the field of foreign languages, linking it not only with the "assignment" of a certain set of language, sociocultural, speech and other knowledge, speech skills and communicative skills, But with the change of his (student) motifs, relations, personal positions acquired by the emotional and evaluative experience, the system of values and meanings.

Also, N. D. Galskova allocates the main strategic goal in the field of foreign languages "... Creating conditions for the personal formation and development of the individual with the help of the language under study".

Nevertheless, competencies remain an important generation element, both successful learning, and create conditions for the personal formation and development of the individual. Summing up the analysis of learning goals, we can say that the current goal of learning foreign languages is an educational result in the unity of communicative and key competencies.

In addition to goals in the technique there is a concept - content. "... under the content of learning is meant what students should be taught, on the basis of which they to educate them, to implement their education and development".

The technique represents the content in the following parameters:

- 1) Speech subject and emotional-holistic attitude to it (value orientation);
- 2) Communicative skills in the main types of speech activities: listening, speaking, reading

and writing;

- 3) Language tools and skills of using them;
- 4) Sociocultural knowledge and skills;
- 5) General-training skills and special (subject) skills.

All components of learning foreign languages are subject to selection. In the end result of this selection, we will have a certain phonetic, lexical, grammatical and thematic minimum, which should be present in the curriculum. N. D. Galskova puts forward the following requirements for the selection of detention of training in foreign languages:

- 1) Putting and conformity to the age of students, their interests and needs, accounting for their real communicative needs.
- 2) Authenticity, the ability to form a holistic picture of the world with a holistic picture of the world, to attach to the cultural heritage, both of the country and the country under study.
- 3) Appeal to the positive feelings of students, their personal experience, value-semantic relationships.
- 4) The focus on the formation of student critical thinking, independence, personal self-identification and reflection.

As we can observe, be a good, modern and professional teacher is not easy. It is also easy to traded the tendency to change the methodological directions that change over time, with the emergence of the new needs of society. Each methodologist, teacher, scientist is trying to find or create the most rational method of teaching foreign languages. When choosing a learning method, it is always necessary to remember that "training is a way of interconnected and interdependent activities of the teacher and students aimed at implementing learning goals".

Thus, considering the psychological features of students, we once again we are convinced that the educational process is aimed at developing a child. When teaching the teacher, it is necessary to take into account many aspects of the psychological development of each learner and it is advisable to build an individual educational route. In addition, it is necessary to properly select the content of learning to motivate learning, both external and internal. The objectives of education in general contribute to the development of the multilateral personality of the study. Despite the rapid development of new methodological approaches and new requirements in training, many competencies, knowledge and skills remain in demand. Therefore, for the successful implementation of individualization in training, the teacher must be able to properly distribute intellectual activity of students, to know their psychological properties, be able to build educational routes and promote the development of not only professional skills, but also "flexible". In order to understand how to properly pave an educational route in the conditions of SES, given all the needs of students, we will consider individualization from various points of view of scientists and methodists.

The concepts of individualization, differentiation and personalization in training.

Modern pedagogy takes a great role of individualization in learning. It is the objectives of training, in general, and English, in particular, are the root cause of individualization allocation. According to scientists, the place of individualization in training is the orientation of the educational process to improve the abilities of students, accounting for their individual characteristics, optimization of various forms and methods of teacher's activities to achieve one goal - to improve personal and professional qualities of students, as well as the development of flexible and professional skills. To date, training, including foreign languages, focuses on an average student, which leads to the fact that the peculiarities of perception, the

rate of assimilation, the motives and the interests of a particular studying do not receive due attention. The relevance of the topic causes a sufficiently large number of interpretations of the concept of "individualization". So, referring to the definition of individualization I. E. Unt, we will get enough compressed version of the interpretation of the concept of individualization of training: "Individualization of training is:

- 1) The organization of the educational process, in which the choice of methods, techniques, the pace of learning is due to individual characteristics of students;
- 2) Various educational, methodological, psychological and pedagogical and organizational management activities that provide an individual approach.

In addition to the concept of "individualization", in pedagogical science, it often operates with the concept of "differentiation". There are three points of view on the interaction of these processes. First, there is a point of view that concepts individualization and learning differentiation are synonymous.

For example, N. M. Shakhmayev, speaking about the educational process for which the taking into account of typical individual differences in students is characterized, calls it differentiated, and schoolchildren's training in the conditions of this process - differentiated learning. Term Differentiation The author interprets as "... such an organization of the educational process, in which the accounting of individual characteristics of students is carried out in the working of teachers in ordinary classes. This is essentially nothing but individualization of learning".

For the first time, the term "personalization" appeared in 1905, when Helen Parkherst offered to use the method known to date as "Dalton-plan". The meaning of this method was that the cabinet was divided into several zones, where there was a certain object in each zone. Thanks to this separation, children could independently or with the help of a teacher choose the most optimal pace for themselves and interact with other students, helping or consulting with them, which contributes to the development of flexible skills, and more precisely - teamwork, the ability to correctly fulfill the target and so on.

A more detailed study of the personalization of learning began only after 65 years. The first to pay attention to personalization and attempted to reveal its essence was the Spanish teacher Viktor Garcia Xotsi. Since then, various interpretations of this term began to appear. The problem is that personalization is built around the idea of choosing information, based on the needs of each studying, highlighting the importance of the maximum disclosure of the child's potential. Ken Robinson, one of the successful figures in the field of education, described the phenomenon of personalization as follows: "In my opinion, personalization in education is to build a process of learning specific disciples, taking into account their strengths and weaknesses, various interests and various ways to master information characteristic of each of them". As we see, the approach of Ken Robinson to personalization echoes the interpretation of the differentiation proposed by I. E. Unt, which determined the concept of differentiation as "... such an organization of the educational process, in which the accounting of individual characteristics of students is carried out in the conditions of teachers in regular classes. This is essentially nothing but individualization of learning".

Personalization in training is not a new approach, but interest is paid to it in recent years. The essence of personalization is that the center of the educational process becomes directly a student, and not standards and learning requirements. Where the individual trajectory is an educational route that suits a specific person, taking into account its features and needs. The

studying itself chooses those items that are most interesting to him and will be useful for further professional activities.

Comparing the processes of individualization, differentiation and personalization, we revealed that the learning process, both when applying differentiation and in the process of individualization, is directed directly to the identity of each student, on its individuality, cognitive and psychological properties and features. And their main difference is that with an individualized approach, pedagogical actions are aimed at a specific student, and during differentiation - on those who are formed by any signs of the group of students.

A modern education system seeks to emphasize on issues related to human personality. However, the objective tendency of the development of culture and society indicates an increase in the innovative elements that individualize human being. Based on the foregoing, it can be said that each educational institution is able to implement the potential of each trainee in practice.

Conclusion

According to SES, modern education is aimed at creating such conditions for the development of the individual, in which each study will be able to realize its potential, and this is impossible without individualization of learning. Individualization is particularly relevant for foreign language learning, since the process of mastering a foreign language is highly depends on personal qualities, individual and subject properties of students.

However, among scientists there is no single opinion, regarding the definition of the entity of individualization. Along with the concept of "individualization", there are also such concepts as "differentiation" and "personalization". A number of scientists practically identify these concepts, however, according to others, they are not identical, although these concepts have a number of similar characteristics. Sharing the point of view of the latter, we in our study adhere to the position that individualization, differentiation and personalization, with the leading role of individualization, can create the most efficient conditions for the learning process, allowing the teacher to make the lesson to create a lesson and create all the conditions for the student selfrealization.

Research and analyzing the experience of implementing the principle of individualization, we can find differences and similarities in the approaches of each teacher. We have convinced that individualization is such a principle in which the teacher must take into account many details, and the most important thing is to correctly choose the tasks and to do with them so that each student has learned the mandatory minimum and he (student) has increased interest in the subject. The whole process of implementing individualization is although it is energy-proof, but it is with its help that it is possible to achieve the highest results in the assimilation of the material to the student.

Summarizing the ideas of individualization, we can state that individualization is the principle of training that implies the creation of a number of conditions that contribute to the effective learning learning material.

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